

The Natural World Connected by Pulses

Junichi Hashimoto
Annaka, Japan

Suggested Citation

Hashimoto, J. (2023). The Natural World Connected by Pulses. *European Journal of Theoretical and Applied Sciences*, 1(6), 564-570. DOI: [10.59324/ejtas.2023.1\(6\).57](https://doi.org/10.59324/ejtas.2023.1(6).57)

Abstract:

Even if this universe is subdivided into smaller scales, it retains a similar structure in the Sun, Earth, human body, atoms, etc. At every scale, its members are bound to each other and form an organic nature. The relationships between such members appear in the form of energy (pulses). Their pulsating and beating nature allows this natural world to continue to operate autonomously. A detailed examination of this has led to a systematic understanding of topics

such as the role of humanity on the planet, the origin of the brain and the nature of desire. Along with such clarification work, theoretical proofs were also provided for the equivalence of electromagnetic waves and pulses, as well as the equivalence of rotation and pulsation. This will have a major impact on various fields in the future.

Keywords: *Relationships, Organicity, Autonomy, Consumption And Decomposition Activities, Track Down.*

Introduction

This world is a clockwork organism, so to speak. This is because this universe exists autonomously, with the various constituent members of it relating to and influencing each other. If this is the case, then matter as a member of the universe should interact with each other, as if the parts inside a clock were intertwined with each other. The interaction between matter and electromagnetic waves is just that. I have revealed its nature through the creation of relational physics. What is derived from this is that force and energy are relationships that link objects to objects (Junichi, 2022). Once such universal criteria for the natural world have been developed, it becomes possible to systematize both the macro and micro worlds from an organic perspective at each scale. Such an organic view of the universe and nature runs throughout this paper. The table can be summarized as follows (Table 1).

Table 1. Hierarchy of Natural Mechanisms

Scales	Mechanisms
Universe	Everything is constantly changing (Relational physics)
Sun	Nuclear fusion activities
Earth	Consumption and decomposition activities
Biological individual (human)	Track down
Atom	Junichi Hashimoto's Law

Through various mechanisms classified and systematized as such, this natural world is harmonized through energy (light, attraction). However, in order to explain each mechanism in detail, scientists have to make significant leaps in logic based on assumed knowledge and data. Starting with the next section, I will look at each one, in detail.

Methodology

It is not easy to know how our universe is structured. However, there are clues. It is the comparison between the Earth and the Sun. We should extract the mechanisms common to both through analyzing the principles on which they operate. From there we can extend the image to the whole universe.

Let us first consider the Sun. It works by radiating light and heat through the transformation of hydrogen atoms into helium atom by nuclear fusion between nuclei (Kenneth, 1997). The Sun can thus be said to be autonomous.

On the other hand, what about the Earth? To think about this, it is necessary to come up with a unique activity for the Earth that is different from that of a star made of gas. This is because the Earth is a terrestrial planet made of soil and rocks. So how can it operate autonomously? The answer is “consumption and decomposition activities”. The Earth is not a fixed star, so it cannot change on its own like the Sun. So, the Earth gave birth to about tens of millions of creatures (Satoshi, 1999) and set up a system to change itself through their consumptive power. The evidence for this is the food chain system that has been established on the planet, with humanity at the top (Shinichi, 2011). For example, small fish eat the plankton that lives in the sea, small fish are eaten by medium-sized fish, medium-sized fish are in turn eaten by large fish, and finally, humans eat them. This is also the case in savannas, where herbivores eat plants, which are in turn eaten by carnivores and humans.

In this way, the creatures carry out various consumption activities, and the terrestrial planet carries out autonomous functions with their help. Come to think of it, the creatures can be found everywhere on Earth - in the air, underwater, underground, and on land. Some of these creatures live in harsher environments than is common knowledge. Some bacteria live by producing methane 2500 meters below the seafloor, and crabs and shellfish live by feeding on hydrogen sulfide near hydrothermal vents on the ocean floor (Newton Press, 2016). As such,

“consumption and decomposition activities” cannot be expected without living organisms everywhere on the planet. That is why the planet is home to about tens of millions of living creatures and 7.8 billion people. Their activities are consuming and decomposing the planet itself, thereby transforming it into a new planet. Humans are outstanding in the extent to which they play this role. In addition to their role at the top of the food chain, they are also responsible for the mass production, consumption and disposal of buildings, vehicles and electrical appliances from raw materials such as metal, stone and wood. So is drilling for fuel resources such as oil and coal. It can all be summed up in terms of large-scale consumption and decomposition activities for the planet. This is parallel to the fusion activity in the Sun.

As described above, it can be seen that both fixed star and terrestrial planets have their own methodologies for realizing autonomy. And if we try to summarize the differences between the autonomous activities of the Earth and the Sun, we can also see that they also have an organic structure. It is the organic nature of the earth and the sun. The structure can be extended to the level of the solar system, to the level of the galaxy and to the level of the entire universe. This is because there is one party as the center and the other party revolving around it, and they all have one thing in common in that they are in harmony.

If so, we can see a similar structure for the microscopic world of molecules and atoms. In this regard, in the basic quantum theory, electrons in atomic structures are denied reality and are viewed as waves (Clifford, 2019). Often, an illustration of this is drawn of electrons covering the nucleus like a cloud, but only the electrons are represented as a cloud. The nucleon is depicted as a particle. If electrons are clouds (waves), then so should nucleons, yet nucleons are depicted as real particles. In other words, quantum theory fails to capture the micro-world in a unified way.

In relational physics, on the other hand, electrons and nucleons are in harmony with each other as entities with existence, and the earth and

sun are in harmony with each other as entities with existence, which is thought to form the solar system model at each scale. Hence, both the micro and macro worlds can be explained without contradiction by a common mechanism.

Why is it that the atomic structure in the micro-world is composed of substantial particles and has a harmonic structure in common with the solar system model? Let us take a closer look at it. When a scientific law is formulated, if it contains a constant, it is based on the degree of immersion, i.e., stability. Whenever such a property is expressed as a function of a new factor, the number of parties, the solution is $n=1$. I named it “Junichi Hashimoto’s Law”. The reason why the behavior of an object described by such a relational expression is stable is that it is one ordered body such that it can be counted as the party number “1” as a whole (Junichi, 2023). It is expressed by the following equation.

$$Const = \frac{1}{i} \times p_m \quad (1)$$

$1/i$ represents the degree of stability, and p_m represents the adjustment parameter to balance both sides.

Now, I would like to derive a new orbital law for the Earth’s motion in the solar system that incorporates Junichi Hashimoto’s Law. The factor used for the standard is the speed of light (c). For the orbit of the earth, a regular circle was set for convenience ($2 \pi l$). Then, assuming that the earth orbits the circular orbit n_c times at the speed of light for a given time, the following equation is given.

$$ct = n_c 2\pi l \quad (2)$$

Since the constant part of the above equation is “ c ”, applying Junichi Hashimoto’s Law, it is expressed by the following equation.

$$c = \frac{1}{i} \times 1 \quad (3)$$

Substituting equation (3) into equation (2) gives the following form.

$$\frac{1}{i} t = n_c 2\pi l \quad (4)$$

In relational physics, stability is expressed as the product of the number of parties and the velocity (Junichi, 2022), so the following process gives an expression for the number of parties that make up the sun-earth relationship.

$$nvt = n_c 2\pi l$$

$$n = \frac{n_c 2\pi l [\text{m}]}{vt [\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1} \cdot \text{s}]}$$

$$n = n_c \frac{2\pi l}{vt} \quad (5)$$

This is the relational expression that can describe the number of parties in the solar system model. Let us assume that the earth orbits around the sun for only one orbit in one year, and calculate the value of the number of parties. Let us set the orbital radius to 149597828677 [m], the orbital velocity to 29780 [$\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}$] (Sigeru, Junichi, & Sho, 2022), and one year to 31558231 [s]. The solution is given by the following process.

$$n = 1 \times \frac{2 \times 3.14 \times 149597828677 [\text{m}]}{29780 [\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}] \times 31558231 [\text{s}]} = 0.9996491$$

As described above, the number of parties constituting the Sun-Earth relationship was found to be “1”. This tells us that the sun and the earth are one ordered body. The stability as a solar system model in which both are interwoven comes from this.

Now, let us verify the atomic model with similar calculations. Specifically, I would like to take the hydrogen atom as my subject. For a detailed data explanation of the numerical values used in the

equation, please refer to my previous paper (Junichi, 2023). Now, let us calculate using equation (5). The solution is given by the following process.

$$n = 1 \times \frac{2.4504937 \times 10^{-10} [\text{m}]}{299792458 [\text{m} \cdot \text{s}^{-1}] \times (8.1739671 \times 10^{-19} [\text{s}])} = 0.9999999$$

Thus, even in the atomic model in which one electron orbits around one proton, the number of parties was found to be “1”. This implies that the proton and electron are one ordered body. One revolution of an electron is equivalent in stability to one rotation of a hydrogen atom. Therefore, we can say that microscopic particles have a certain reality, just as the sun and the earth do.

As described above, it can be seen that both the atomic model and the solar system model operate on the same system. And the source that forms it is attraction and light. Both were unified as the same in relational physics (Junichi, 2022). Both are the same in that they are relationships between objects. The criterion for distinction is distance. Roughly speaking, the relationship linking micro distances appears as attraction, while the relationship linking macro distances appears as light. The universe, the solar system, and the terrestrial ecosystem are all bound by such light and attraction to form an organic structure. At the same time, it creates autonomy in nature.

Discussion

The universe, the solar system, the earth's environment, and atomic structure are all organic in nature, and furthermore, they stand in a hierarchical similarity to each other across scales. In other words, the universe, the solar system, the terrestrial ecosystem, and the atomic structure are similar to each other, albeit at different scales.

Then, do the brains and bodies of humans and animals really have similar systems to those? In this section, I would like to discuss the

mechanism of autonomous harmonization of the human body.

As mentioned above, the sun generates autonomy through nuclear fusion activities, and the earth achieves autonomy through consumption and decomposition activities by living creatures. How, then, does the human body continue to operate autonomously? To answer this, it is necessary to extract universal laws from limited individual knowledge inductively. In doing so, a rather bold leap of logic will be required. The premise, then, is an understanding of the origin of the brain. Some living creatures have brains, others do not. Unicellular organisms such as amoebas do not have them, but multicellular organisms tend to begin to have brains as their total number of cells increases. In light of the above, the brain is a group of nerve cells that serves as the center of many body cells and is the highest decision-making organ (command center) that determines the direction of the individual. It is like the head of state or the government of a nation. Conversely, unicellular organisms do not have a brain because they do not need to organize a large number of member cells. Thus, a comparison of unicellular and multicellular organisms provides an answer to the question of why the brain exists in living things.

Then, with the origin of the brain now clear, it is necessary to consider the relationship between brain cells and somatic cells. This is because, in order for living creatures to maintain their unity as individuals, they must have some sort of communication mechanism in place between them. The clarification of this will provide us with a deeper insight into the organic nature of the human brain and body, and the autonomy that arises from it.

So what is the mechanism that relates brain cells and somatic cells to each other? Earlier, I mentioned that the brain is the command center for many body cells. To be so, the brain must be a source of information backed by a rich network. Such neural networks form the order in the brain, so to speak. It is constantly renewing its order content through daily experience and learning. The object of

transmission of its contents is the somatic cell, the germ cell. The knowledge and know-how acquired by the brain, which is useful for the survival of the individual, only makes sense when it is immediately transformed into information and transmitted throughout the body. There should be no time lag between the transmission of information by the brain and its reception (information renewal) by the body cells. All things are in flux, and the natural environment and social conditions surrounding the human body are constantly changing from moment to moment. Therefore, if there is a time lag, we are left behind in the flow of change.

Thus, in order to maintain unity as an individual organism, the human body constantly maintains close coordination between brain cells and body cells. So, specifically, what mechanism do they follow to achieve this? The key to solving this is the new theory I advocate. The example that led to its birth is the recording that takes place in the songwriting studio. Musicians record the final sound source for the backing track to master tape, all at once, in one fell swoop. The process is called “track down”. Inspired by this, a new hypothesis was born, which I named the “Track Down Theory”. The brain is triggered by widespread and intense excitation, and the daily shifting order (neural networks) in the brain tracks down the latest information to germ cells and body cells throughout the body in one fell swoop. This constant writing of information allows the human body to always maintain an up-to-date state and thus keep up with the flow of changes in the surrounding environment.

In this regard, the human body is designed to obtain great pleasure (intense brain excitation) primarily when eating, sleeping, or engaging in sexual activity. Originally, the number of nerve cells (neurons) in the human brain was said to be about 14 billion in the neocortex alone, and about 100 billion in the entire brain (Newton Press, 2016). The order in the brain is a complex one, composed of a vast number of such neurons and their knots, the synapses (Hiroyoshi, & Masashi, 2003). In order to synchronize it instantly, it is necessary to generate a great pleasure that violently excites the entire brain. As evidence, the human brain is

designed to feel great pleasure through the release of the neurotransmitter dopamine to various parts of the brain by the pleasure nerves (A10 nerves), which are comprehensively spread over all its regions (Nobuko, 2014). In this light, we can see that the instinctive human appetites for sex, food, and sleep are for this purpose, and are the source power of the track down.

The content, frequency, and degree of such pleasurable behaviors vary from person to person. The nerve pulses generated in the human body are transmitted within nerve cells in the form of electrical signals (Takeshi, 2020), and their intensity, frequency, and transmission speed are also thought to vary from person to person. In this regard, the transmission speed is generally around $120 \text{ [m}\cdot\text{s}^{-1}]$ (Takeshi, 2020). Compared to the transmission speed of electromagnetic waves (Physics Dictionary Member of Editorial Board Meeting, 1986), this is significantly slower. In relational physics, which I founded, factors such as the intensity, frequency, and transmission speed of electromagnetic waves are all affected by a unique factor called the number of parties (Junichi, 2022). Thus, the factors that slow down the rate of nerve pulse transmission in the human body are the large number of cells that make up the human body and the amount of substances present in the cells.

There are individual differences in hedonic behavior, as noted earlier. If so, there will be individual differences in terms of what the associated track down will be and what the physical consequences will be. Daily physical condition, facial features, body shape, abilities and competence, development and aging, and the amount of pheromones emitted are all dependent on it. Although not discussed in detail here, the mechanism of cancer development can also be explained within the same framework. In other words, continued exposure to excessive track down stimuli damages the DNA of somatic cells and induces copying errors during cell division. This causes the cells to become cancerous.

Thus, track down affects even a person’s health and longevity, which is precisely what

determines an individual's destiny and happiness.

That being the case, if you want to keep your health, youthfulness, and beauty, you need to optimize the hedonic behaviors that are the source of track down.

Brain cells and somatic cells are linked and united by such pleasurable behavior. It is what allows the human body to operate autonomously.

Next, let us consider what we can see when we generalize the properties of electrical pulses generated by the human body to electromagnetic waves. As introduced in Table 1, the mechanisms that govern the universe, the sun, the earth, and the human body are all self-similar, albeit on different scales. This raises the question of whether there is any commonality between pulses and electromagnetic waves.

In this regard, electromagnetic waves are generally considered to propagate through space with alternating production of electric and magnetic fields, but they do not come in an uninterrupted manner (Valerie, 2012). In contrast, a pulse is generally considered to be a periodic repetition of a state in which the signalized energy comes to 100 % and then stops and goes to 0 %.

From the above contrast, it would seem at first glance the electromagnetic waves and pulses are two different things. However, relational physics does not take such a position. Let us take a closer look at it. This theory states that electromagnetic waves are relationships between objects. The establishment of it is immediately completed simply by the mere presence of the object and the object there. This means that the transfer speed is theoretically infinite. Strictly speaking, however, it is not the case that electromagnetic waves leave one object, travel through space toward the other object, and reach the receiving object after 0 seconds have elapsed. It is something that originally connects both objects as if it were a single line. It is not a model where something moves from one end to the other.

Then, from such characteristics of electromagnetic waves, it is still different from

pulse? As it turns out, it is not. Indeed, electromagnetic waves conclude between objects without any time lag. However, it is not constant. Just as the nerve pulses in the human body do, the matter that is the source of energy changes periodically (Junichi, 2022). In light of this, the electromagnetic waves themselves, dragged along by their rhythmic nature, will alternately connect and disconnect between objects. It is thought that the cycle is extremely short, and is rhythmic at interval as close to zero seconds as possible. Hence, it is difficult for humans to measure it. Nevertheless, we can recognize a pulse there, as long as it alternates between "conclusion" and "nonconclusion".

Thus, electromagnetic waves are also pulses in a broad sense.

In nature, whether it is the universe, the sun, the earth, the human body, or atoms, pulses connect objects to form organic structures, and furthermore, their pulsations create autonomy. All things flow, that is what it means.

Results

To explore the universal mechanisms that govern the natural world, I have attempted to compare star and terrestrial planets, unicellular and multicellular organisms, brain cells and somatic cells. As a result, it became clear that objects are organically connected to each other and that autonomous activities emerge from such structures. It was also confirmed that the solar system model and the atomic model are the same in such respects. Furthermore, it was found that pulses and electromagnetic waves are the same in that they originate from the pulsating nature of the source material and that energy is released from it in a pulsating manner. In addition, although not detail in this paper, the rotation of an object can be regarded as equivalent to its pulsation. For example, as the earth rotates on its axis, it alternates between day and night, which is truly a pulsation. If so, based on the aforementioned context, both the energy produced from the spinning motion of matter and the energy produced from the vibrating or stretching motion of matter would be

interpreted as being pulsating.

Based on the above findings, a new picture of the universe will be created. That is, the depiction of the “natural world connected by pulses”, which is also expressed in the title of this paper. Everything can be explained on the basis of such the most universal concept in human history.

Conclusion

This world is a clockwork organism, so to speak. In this respect, the sun and the earth have the same structure. Both celestial bodies create autonomy from such structures, but when we consider Earth’s own autonomous activities, the significance of human existence emerges from this. In other words, we humans are the bearers of large-scale and sophisticated “consumption and decomposition activities” on the earth. And when we look at the autonomy of the human body, we realize that close coordination between brain cells and body cells is essential for it to function, and that intense pleasure must be generated in the brain in order to carry this out efficiently. From this, logically and inevitably, the nature of the desires that human beings have is determined. In other words, the strong desire for food, sex, sleep, etc., is for the purpose of transforming into a new self through “track down”. If so, then all human desires can be summed up in terms of the desire for transformation. Thanks to it, this earth revolve and this universe revolve.

References

- Clifford, A.P (2019). *Visual History of Physics*. Iwanami Shoten Publishers, p. 161.
- Hiroyoshi, M., & Masashi, I. (2003). *Biophysics of Neurons*. Maruzen Publishing Co., Ltd., p. 68.
- Junichi, H. (2022). Theory of Everything. *Journal of Innovations in Energy science*, 2(3), pp. 2-3, 10, 25-30, 41.
- Junichi, H. (2023). Junichi Hashimoto’s Law. *Fundamental Journal of Modern Physics*, 19(2), 10-11, 24.
- Kenneth, R.L. (1997). *The Sun: Its True Face and Its Relationship to the Global Environment*. Springer-Verlag Tokyo, Inc., p. 29.
- Newton Press. (2016). *Amazing Bacteria*. Newton Press, pp. 54-55, 62-65.
- Newton Press. (2016). *Brain and Neuron*. Newton Press, pp. 14, 110.
- Nobuko, N. (2014). *Brain Drugs*. Gentosha Inc., pp. 28-31.
- Physics Dictionary Member of Editorial Board Meeting. (1986). *Physics Dictionary*. Baifukan, p. 2300.
- Satoshi, I. (1999). *Bacteria*. Nippon Jitsugyo Publishing, p.12.
- Shinichi, M. (2011). *A Great Study in the Food Chain*. PHP., p. 8.
- Sigeru, I., Junichi, W., & Sho, S. (2022). *Sun and Planets*. Nippon Hyoron sha. 2nd. ed., p.311.
- Takeshi, S. (2020). *Understanding and Loving Neuroscience*. Yodosha Co., Ltd., pp. 34-35, 41-43.
- Valerie, I. (2012). *The Penguin Dictionary of PHYSICS*. Fourth edition, p. 269.